

SSL method slideshow

“READ ME”

Guide for SSL using example data provided in dryad

Overall Schematic of methods

Links to resources

Acoustic recordings can be downloaded from SanctSound portal:

- <https://sanctsound.portal.axds.co/>

Denoise through RRPCA script in dryad folder:

- “SSL_RPCA.R”
- Using example data: “SDT_BF_01_PSD_20min_20Hz”
- Example output tpws file: (this is how matrix needs to be formatted after output of RRPCA produced)
 - “LR_BF_01_TPWS1.mat”

Toolkit for calculating matrix of sound levels “soundscape metrics”, clustering, and neural net

- <https://github.com/MarineBioAcousticsRC/Triton>
- Explanation of Triton toolboxes can be found in the wiki:
 - <https://github.com/MarineBioAcousticsRC/Triton/wiki>

Feature Preparation: Calculate Matrix of Sound Levels from Long Term Spectral Averages

- <https://github.com/MarineBioAcousticsRC/Triton>
- Use Triton's "Soundscape LTSA" Package to
 - 1) Create "Soundscape LTSA" and
 - 2) "Compute Soundscape Metrics"
 - See next slide for example settings used

Feature Preparation: Example Settings

Soundscape LTSA Settings

Input Directory

Output Directory

Output Filename

LTSA Parameters

Averaging Time [s]	<input type="text" value="1"/>	File type: 1=WAV, 2=XWAV	<input type="text" value="2"/>
Frequency bin size [Hz]	<input type="text" value="1"/>	Data Type: 1=HARP, 5=SoundTrap	<input type="text" value="1"/>
Length of LTSA [days]	<input type="text" value="7"/>	Data Channel Number	<input type="text" value="1"/>
Start with LTSA #	<input type="text" value="1"/>		

Compute Soundscape Metrics - v1.0

Save/Load Settings

Compute Soundscape Metrics Settings

Directory with LTSA(s)

Output Directory

Input Start and Output File Types

Start with Input File [no.] CSV File LTSA File

Data Analysis Parameters

Bandpass Edges		Analysis Type	
Low Frequency Limit [Hz]	<input type="text" value="20"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Broadband Level	<input type="checkbox"/> Octave Level
High Frequency Limit [Hz]	<input type="text" value="1000"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Third Octave Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Power Spectral Density
Averaging		Averaging Type	
Bin Size Time [sec]	<input type="text" value="1200"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Mean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Median
PSD Bin Size Frequency [Hz]	<input type="text" value="20"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Percentiles	
Min. Seconds/Average [%]	<input type="text" value="50"/>	Remove Erroneous Data	
		<input type="checkbox"/> Remove FIFO	<input type="checkbox"/> Remove Disk Writes HARP
		<input type="checkbox"/> Remove Flow/Strumming	

Data Calibration

Calibrate Data

Single Value

System Sensitivity (dB) Transfer Function

*Note this example uses PSD median values for 20 Hz and 20 minute binning, but can change values and binning based on feature of interest!

Denoising: RRPCA– denoises data of transients

Denoise through RRPCA script in dryad folder:

- “SSL_RPCA.R”
- Using example data: “SDT_BF_01_PSD_20min_20Hz”

Partitioning: Unsupervised Clustering: identify distinct classes of chorus and noise

- <https://github.com/MarineBioAcousticsRC/Triton>
- Use “Cluster Bin Tool” and “Composite Clustering Tool” to identify distinct classes of chorus and noise.
- Input uses matrices from RRPCA output. These matrices are saved into “TPWS files.” Example TPWS file provided in dryad for formatting purposes.
 - TPWS file called: “LR_BF_01_TPWS1.mat”
- See next slide for example settings

Clustering: Example Settings

Cluster Bin Tool - v1.0

Save/Load Settings

Verify Bin Clustering Options

TPWS Input Folder

Search Sub-Folders

Output Folder

TPWS Name Wildcard TPWS Iteration Number

Clustering Parameters

Cluster on Spectra

Start Freq (kHz) End Freq (kHz)

Compare spectra in linear space

Compare spectra on first derivative

Cluster on Waveform

Normalize Amplitudes

Min. Cluster Size

Pruning Threshold [0-100] Percentage

Time bin size (minutes)

Peak-To-Peak Ampl. Threshold

Max ICI (Sec)

Min Cue Gap (Sec)

Clustering Options & Performance Settings

Show plots during execution

Pause after plotting

Remove labeled false positives from detEdit

Merge nodes

Parallel pool size

Max Clustering Iterations

Max Network Size

Run Cluster Bins

Composite Clustering Tool - v1.0

Save/Load Settings

Verify Composite Clustering Options

Input Folder

Input File Name Wildcard

Output Folder

Output File Name

Save Output

Feature Selection

Compare on spectra

Min. Freq. (kHz) Max. Freq. (kHz)

Compare 1st deriv. Linear space

Normalize mean spectra

Compare on temporal features

Min ICI (sec) Max ICI (sec)

Compare on waveform

Thresholds & Constants

Max Clustering Iterations

Max Network Size

Pruning Threshold [0-100]

Min. Bin Size

Min. Cluster Size

Number of Trials

Cluster Pruning Factor [0-.99]

Use Only Clustered Bins

Use Only Single Cluster Bins

Remove bins similar to unwanted clusters

Run Composite Clustering

*Note, clustering settings can be changed based on feature of interest (pruning threshold, normalization, etc)

Train Neural Network

- Train neural network using clusters
- <https://github.com/MarineBioAcousticsRC/Triton>
- Use Triton's "Neural Net" Package to train and run neural network
- See example settings on next page

Neural Net Training and design: settings

Saved previously named clusters to folder labeled “My Clusters” under two folders

1. Chorus
2. Noise

The screenshot shows the 'Train and Test Set Options' dialog box. The 'Data Type' section has 'Bin Level' selected. The 'Input Base Folder' is a text field. The 'Bin File Wildcard' is '*binLevel.mat' and the 'Detection File Wildcard' is '*detLevel.mat'. The 'Output Folder' is a text field. The 'Output File Name' is 'Nnet_SDT_SOCAL_800hz'. The '% of Dataset for Training' is 60 and the 'Max Training Set Size' is 1000. The '% of Dataset for Validation' is 10. The 'Bout Gap (minutes)' is 20. There is an 'Add Noise' checkbox. The 'Train on:' section has 'Spectra' selected, and 'Waveform' and 'ICI' are unselected. A green 'Run' button is at the bottom.

The screenshot shows the 'Network Design Options' dialog box. The 'Train Data File', 'Test Data File', 'Validation Data File', and 'Output Folder' are all text fields. Below these is a section titled 'Network Configuration' with a yellow background. It contains 'Hidden Layers' (4), 'Hidden Layer Size' (128), 'Dropout Rate' (50), 'Batch Size' (50), and 'Epochs' (15). There is a 'Save figures' checkbox which is checked. A green 'Run' button is at the bottom.

Neural Net: Classification Settings

Neural Net Tool - v1.0: Classify

Classification Options

Bins Detections

Location of 'Cluster Bins' output:

Search subfolders

Show intermediate plots

Trained Network File Path:

Output Folder:

Neural Net Tool - v1.0: Export DetEdit ID File(s)

Export Network Labels to DetEdit ID Format

Bins Detections

Folder of Network Classification Output (bin):

Filename Wildcard (optional)

Output Folder:

Visualize labels on LTSA

- Can use “label vis” package within triton to visualize neural net labels on LTSA.
- <https://github.com/MarineBioAcousticsRC/Triton>
- See example settings:

The screenshot shows a dialog box titled "Create tLabs from detEdit Output" with a subtitle "tLab Creation Settings". The dialog is divided into two sections: "Load/Save Paths" (highlighted in green) and "Other Settings" (highlighted in red).

Load/Save Paths:

- Input Folder: [Redacted]
- File Type: TPWS detEdit ID File detEdit FD File detEdit TD File
- TPWS Iteration: 1
- Output Directory: [Redacted]
- Input File Prefix: LR_GR_01

Other Settings:

- Label Name: true
- Time Offset: 2000
- Click Duration: 1200

At the bottom, there is a yellow button labeled "Create tLab ...".